

Table 2 continued

Cluster	Genotype	Areas of cultivation	Days to		Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle (no.)	Productive tillers/plant (no.)	Straw yield/plant (g)	Grain yield/plant (g)
			50% flowering I	Maturity II						
IV	PBNR89-6, K35-3	Marathwada (Parbhani), Konkan (Ratnagiri)	86.00 -	112.50 -	77.75 -	18.20 <u>(5.56)</u>	80.70 (15.25)	9.08 (23.55)	9.11 (8.16)	18.68 -
V	PBNR88-4	Marathwada (Parbhani)	98.50 -	127.00 -	71.40 -	19.50 -	86.50 <u>(0.00)</u>	7.59 (14.21)	5.36 (17.71)	9.30 -
VI	Krishna Sal	Western Maharashtra (Ahmednager)	101.00 -	130.00 -	93.40 -	18.70 -	88.40 -	10.08 <u>(0.00)</u>	9.90 (25.02)	22.87 -
VII	Ambika	Marathwada (Parbhani)	85.00 -	113.00 -	83.50 -	16.50 -	52.50 -	58.41 -	12.15 <u>(0.00)</u>	12.22 -
	Pooled mean	-	94.34	123.90	77.67	17.78	74.76	8.80	8.74	13.96

Figures in parentheses are intercluster D values. Underlined figures in parentheses are intracluster D values. Figures without parentheses are mean performance values.

When planning hybridization programs to achieve early flowering and maturity, varieties from Cluster VII (Ambika) may be used; for dwarfness, Clusters I and VI;

for panicle length, Cluster VI (Krishna Sal); for filled grains/panicle, Cluster VI (Krishna Sal); for productive tillers/plant, Cluster IV (PBNR89-6 and K35-3); and

for straw yield/plant, Cluster VII (Ambika). ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Strain differentiation of rice tungro bacilliform virus by restriction fragment length analysis of polymerase chain reaction-amplified products

A. C. Dolores-Talens, J. R. Escara-Wilke, P. Q. Cabauatan, R. J. Nelson, and H. Koganezawa, IRRRI

Tungro is the most important disease of rice in South and Southeast Asia. A composite of two viruses, rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV), causes the disease. Multiple strains of RTBV, a double-stranded DNA virus, have been reported recently. Each of the strains, L, G1, G2, and Ic, manifests distinct symptoms on rice cultivars FK135 and Taichung Native 1. Strain Ic induced interveinal chlorosis, stunting, reduced tillering, and narrowing of leaves. G1 and G2 induced only mild stunting. The symptoms caused by these strains were not as severe as those manifested by type strain L.

Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and subsequent restriction enzyme digestion were used to investigate molecular variations among the strains. Specific segments of the viral genome were amplified by PCR using oligonucleotide primers designed on the basis of published sequence data for RTBV.

The amplified region spanned the intergenic region of the virus with the left, or sense strand, primer (5'-TTACAGAAGGATTGTGAACCC-

3') located within open reading frame 2 (ORF2) and the right, or antisense strand, primer (5'-ACTATAGCTCCTGCTGAACTA-3') located within ORF4 (Fig. 1). Using these primers, a 2.4-kb fragment of RTBV DNA was amplified. Standard PCR conditions were used with 1-10 ng total genomic DNA extract of rice plant tissue and 50 pM primers. The amplified products were resolved on a 2% agarose gel and visualized by staining with

1. Map of the RTBV genome, indicating location of primers used and fragment amplified. (ORF = open reading frame, P = protein.)

2. (a) The 2.4-kb product of amplification using PCR from four RTBV strains. (b) The restriction digestion profiles of the 2.4-kb PCR product for the four virus strains using *Accl*, *Alul*, and *EcoRI*.

ethidium bromide and viewing under ultraviolet light (Fig. 2).

To confirm that amplified products were from the virus being studied, Southern blotting was performed using a labeled DNA probe of the 2.4-kb amplified fragment of the reference strain of RTBV and the labeled DNA of the entire reference strain of the virus (data not shown).

Agarose gel electrophoresis did not distinguish the PCR fragments amplified from the four strains (Fig. 2a). Upon digestion with *AccI*, *AluI*, and *EcoRI*, however, variations among the strains were evident (Fig. 2b). Three DNA banding patterns were observed with each of the enzymes used. Strains G₂ and I₂ could not be differentiated by this method.

This information on molecular variation among the four RTBV strains can be used for diagnosis of virus strains. Further studies are needed to determine the molecular basis of the distinct symptoms incited by each strain. ■

Neck blast-resistant lines of Radha-17 isolated

B. Chaudhary, National Maize Research Program (NMRP), Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Rampur; P. B. Karki, National Grain Legume Research Program, Rampur; and K. K. Lal, NMRP, ARS, Rampur, Nepal

Rice blast (BI), caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav., is one of the most serious rice diseases in Nepal. Blast can reduce yields by 50% in areas where Masuli, Nepal's most popular variety, is grown.

Masuli and Mallika were crossed to develop Radha-17, which has a yield potential of 4 t/ha and resists leaf BI. Radha-17 was reported to be susceptible to neck BI, another serious disease. We have been working to purify neck BI-resistant lines of Radha-17.

We selected 100 disease-free panicles of Radha-17 grown in farmers' field trials in 1990. Seeds from these panicles were sown at 10-cm spacing in 1-m rows (panicle to row) in 1991. The trial plot was surrounded by two rows of a BI-

susceptible variety and by four rows of *Sesbania aculeata*, which were planted 2 and 4 wk before Radha-17, respectively. The seedbed was inoculated uniformly with 1-yr-old BI-infected rice leaf debris.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 1-m rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing in a field fertilized with 120 kg N/ha and 26.4 kg P/ha. The experiment was inoculated twice at tillering and panicle initiation stages by uniformly spreading chopped pieces of fresh BI-infected leaves. Disease rating was scored at maturity using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES).

Only 60 of the 100 lines were selected as resistant in 1991. Seeds from these lines were sown in 1992 in single rows with BI-susceptible variety Masuli in alternate rows at 10-cm spacing. All other activities were the same as in 1991.

While Masuli was severely affected by leaf BI at the seedling stage, leaf BI scores in all test lines were less than three on the SES scale. Neck BI scores were 0-5 in 1991 and 0-7 in 1992; 37 lines

were rated as moderately to highly resistant. The other 23 showed susceptible reactions in 1992.

These results suggest that line Radha-17 is not pure with respect to BI resistance. Selection within populations of similar lines might yield BI-resistant materials. ■

Screening rice accessions for resistance to rice tungro

N. Subramanian, R. Saroja, A. Thyagarajan, K. Nilakantapillai, and M. Subramanian, Rice Research Station (RRS), Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Tirur 602025, Chengalpattu-MGR District, India

A severe outbreak of rice tungro (RTD) disease occurred on susceptible varieties ADT36, TKM9, CO 37, IR64, ASD16, and ASD18 in Chengalpattu-MGR District during 1992 sornavari season (Apr/May-Aug/Sep). Disease incidence was 60-85% at RRS. Light trap catches and in situ counts revealed that the vector, green leafhopper (GLH)